

Screening and experimental evaluation of materials for water harvesting within Direct Air Capture thermally-driven cycles

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Abstract

Direct Air Capture (DAC) of CO₂ from atmospheric air is becoming a crucial topic. One of the main requirements for DAC systems to drive their practical application is the low energy needed for the process and the possible integration with other energy processes. Among the different routes, physical adsorption of CO₂ from air has a promising potential, but still suffers some limitations, since its technological and economical feasibility is linked to the possibility of using low-temperature heat for driving the process with relevant efficiency. One of the main issues encountered in these type of systems is the presence of humidity in the air. Due to the much higher partial pressure of water compared to CO₂, this leads to a negligible CO₂ adsorption if a proper pre-treatment to reduce air humidity is not carried out. Within this paper, we discuss the materials screening and first experimental testing in relevant scale for a water harvesting pre-treatment for the integration of DAC units. To this aim, the theoretical water uptake to significantly reduce humidity is evaluated and different commercial and composite materials have been evaluated. Subsequently, the tests in a dedicated bench at CNR-ITAE to actually evaluate the dynamic of the process are presented.

Keywords: direct air capture; water harvesting; materials screening; composite materials

Introduction

The increasing concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere due to human activities has led to significant concerns about global warming and climate change. Direct air capture (DAC) of CO₂ has emerged as a promising technology to mitigate the effects of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions on the environment.

Thermally-driven DAC is a type of DAC that uses heat to drive the CO₂ capture process, by means of a temperature swing between an adsorption and desorption step. The use of heat in the capture process makes thermally-driven DAC particularly attractive since it allows for the use of low-grade heat sources, such as waste heat from industrial processes, solar thermal energy, or geothermal energy. In recent years, thermally-driven DAC has received increasing attention due to its potential for high CO₂ capture rates, low energy consumption, and the utilization of renewable energy sources. However, significant research efforts are still required to optimize and scale-up thermally-driven DAC processes, and improve their economic feasibility.

One of the main limiting issues is the need to significantly reduce the amount of water in the air before CO₂ adsorption. Indeed, the amount of water needed in the is order of magnitudes less than the amount in the inlet air, therefore highlighting the need for deep air drying.

Aim of the present paper is to discuss the selection of materials suitable for such deep drying stage. To this aim, dedicated equilibrium curves measurements were carried out and the results of a thermodynamic and dynamic analysis are presented.

Material selection and preparation

The material selection was carried out in vision of the practical application of such pre-treatment units in the specific context of a DAC system. Therefore, the following constraints were considered:

- Low regeneration temperature;
- Commercial availability of the material or its main components (in the case of composites);
- Possible integration within heat exchangers either as a coated layer or loose grains.

To this aim, a preliminary selection was carried out starting from either results of previous tests are CNR-ITAE or dedicated measurements. The materials selected include: Siogel® from OkerChemie, SAPO34 zeotype, SAPO5 zeotype, and two composites made using silica gel as matrix and CaCl₂ and LiCl inorganic salts. The preparation method for the composites is described in (Frazzica et al., 2020).

Experimental tests were carried out using the Dynamic gravimetric vapor sorption analyzer (DVS) equipment from Surface Measurement Systems. In particular, the effect of low relative pressure (corresponding to the case of low relative humidity in the air) was evaluated with dedicated testing.

Thermodynamic evaluation

Thermodynamic evaluation was carried out by evaluating the achievable water uptake for the selected materials. In order to get a correspondence between the water uptake in the adsorbent and the relative humidity of the air, the methodology proposed in (Aristov & Gordeeva, 2022) was used, which consists in the superposition of the isosteric curves of the adsorbent with the psychrometric chart of humid air. The method mainly consists of the following steps:

1. Measurement of equilibrium curves (isobars or isotherms) for the adsorbent;
2. Calculation of isosteric lines $P_{wa}(T)|_{w=const}$, where P is the pressure (bar), T is the temperature (K) and w is the water uptake (g/g). In order to calculate them, a fitting on the isotherms or isobars was carried out using Python software and Scipy package.
3. Calculation of the lines at constant relative humidity $T(x)|_{RH=const}$, where x is the humidity ratio (g/g) and can be calculated starting from equilibrium data of the material as $x = \frac{M_{wa}P_{wa}}{M_{da}P_{da}}$, where M is the molar mass (g/mol) and “wa” and “da” refer to water and dry air, respectively.
4. Superposition of these lines on the psychrometric chart of the air. This step was carried out in Python using the psychrochart package.

An example of the results is shown in Figure 1, where the initial and final conditions for the theoretical process are also identified. Initial conditions selected (air temperature of 35°C and 60%RH) are considered representative of summer conditions in Mediterranean climates. As exiting condition, a relative humidity of 1% was considered, which would allow for an efficient adsorption of CO₂ in the subsequent step of the process, thus expecting up to 4.5 mol_{CO2}/kg_{sorbent}.

Figure 1. Thermodynamic evaluation by combination of isosteric lines and psychrometric chart. The case of Siogel.

Using this methodology, a comparison of the materials selected was carried out. The results are reported in Table 1. As it is possible to notice, the Silica gel/CaCl₂ composite shows the highest differential uptake and, at the same time, the lower regeneration temperature to reach the expected w_{dry} . SAPO5 could also represent an interesting alternative, whereas SAPO34 and Siogel® would need extremely high regeneration temperatures. Moreover, Siogel® is also the material with the lowest differential uptake under the expected conditions.

Table 1. Results of the thermodynamic screening.

	w_humid, g/g	w_dry, g/g	Δw , g/g	Expected regeneration T
Siogel®	0.22	0.03	0.18	140°C
Silica gel/CaCl ₂ 25% wt	0.39	0.07	0.32	100°C
SAPO34 (Fahrenheit)	0.29	0.03	0.26	150°C
SAPO5 (Fahrenheit)	0.25	0.03	0.22	120°C

Dynamic evaluation

Dynamic evaluation will be carried out at CNR-ITAE using a dedicated testing rig, whose rendering is presented in Figure 2. It mainly consists of a channel for the air to be pre-treated, which can be assembled in different sections, in order to have the flexibility of testing heat exchangers in different sizes. Since the regeneration of the adsorbent will be carried out using water as HTF for heating up

the material, hydraulic connections for thermostatic baths have been foreseen. Sensors to be installed include temperature, %RH, pressure difference and air velocity. The desired air flow rate will be guaranteed using a fan connected to a variable speed controller. The first testing activity will be carried out on a heat exchanger with Siogel in loose grains, which will represent the benchmarking material, followed by dedicated experiments with SAPO5/ SAPO34 coatings and the composites with loose grain configuration.

Figure 2. The testing rig for dynamic evaluation of materials at CNR ITAE. 1. Fan; 2. Channel for the air in different sections, selected according to the dimension of the heat exchanger to be tested; 3. Heat exchanger to be tested; 4 hydraulic connections to thermostatic baths; 5. Sensors.

On—going activities and future perspectives

In conclusion, this paper presents the preliminary activity for the selection of an adsorbent material for air pre-treatment in a DAC unit. To this aim, several candidates were selected and their equilibrium properties were measured. Subsequently, a thermodynamic analysis was carried out to identify the expected Δw under the operating conditions, i.e. inlet air of 35°C and $\Delta\%RH=59\%$. Results indicated that silica gel/ CaCl_2 composite and SAPO5 have a promising potential, but their dynamic performances need to be assessed. Tests are on-going in a dedicated testing bench and will complete the characterization procedure, including also the selection of loose grains or coating configuration.

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